

ADDITIVE LAYER MANUFACTURING OF COMPOSITE COMPONENTS: COMBINING SHORT FIBRE COMPOSITE FEEDSTOCKS WITH CURVED LAYER FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION

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ABSTRACT

Fused filament fabrication (FFF) is a low cost additive manufacturing technique capable of constructing detailed components from 3D data in a wide range of feedstock materials. The use of short fibre composites in FFF has recently been shown to introduce alignment of short fibres within individual extruded tracks of components manufactured using this technique. Curved layer FFF (CLFFF) is the process of including dynamic z movements to individual layers in FFF in order to improve surface finish and mechanical performance of FFF components. This method shifts from traditional methods that use static z values and manufacture components from flat layers that typically exhibit an inherent weakness in the z direction across individual layer boundaries. This study demonstrates the use of CLFFF in tandem with a composite feedstock consisting of a Nylon PA6 thermoplastic matrix reinforced with 30 wt% short glass fibres. Test specimens are manufactured following ASTM D638 using conventional and CLFFF toolpathing techniques. Preliminary results have indicated promising mechanical properties of manufactured parts under tensile load, although CLFFF components only demonstrated 70 % of the performance of their conventional counterparts. Electron microscopy of fractured sample surfaces has also been conducted and has revealed local alignment of short glass fibres within the vector direction of the extruded tracks of the composite feedstock material.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF), or Fused Deposition Modelling, is a low cost deposition based additive manufacturing technique that allows the fabrication of complex geometries from three dimensional CAD data [1]. The process relies on the deposition of a feedstock material from a mobile tool head which can be precisely controlled within the build volume of the machine. In order to construct components 3D models are converted into detailed toolpaths by slicing the model into uniform layers and then plotting each layer as a series of individual extruded tracks. The simplicity and low cost of this technique has seen it emerge as the leading method for consumer and low cost additive manufacturing in recent years. Consequently it has been the subject of significant interest amongst many researchers and a wide range of process developments have emerged. These advances include various hardware improvements, such as the fashioning of parallel robots for improved manufacturing flexibility and speed [2], as well as the development of a vast range of feedstock materials. These feed stocks are beginning to find useful applications in additive manufacturing and a recent example can be seen in conductive feed stocks that are designed for the manufacture of electrical circuits when used in tandem with an insulating feedstock, representing an example of a functional circuit printed using FFF [3]. Other examples demonstrate the mechanical reinforcement of feedstock materials through the inclusion of short fibre fillers in polymer matrices. Recently for example Compton et al. [4] carried out the deposition of short fibre reinforced epoxy ink that

demonstrated the mechanical benefits of including fillers in FFF feed stocks and the alignment of deposited short fibres during extrusion.

Typically the effective use of composite materials in additive manufacturing is limited although some examples do exist across the additive manufacturing spectrum, for example the use of short carbon fibre reinforcements in Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) feed stocks [5] or ceramic reinforced resins in Stereolithography (SL) processes [6]. Although various studies detail mechanical reinforcement of components using composite feed stocks in FFF [1,7] they also highlight a limitation of the effectiveness of such fillers as an inherent result of the FFF process. The manufacturing of useful short fibre composite materials relies on the uniform reinforcement of a matrix material through the formation of a homogenous mixture during processing [8]. Conversely in current SLS and SL composite processing the maximum size or reinforcing fillers is typically limited by the z layer resolution of the process and consequently provides less inter-layer reinforcement to the final processed material than is desired. The deposition of individual extruded tracks in FFF also leads to inherent weaknesses in manufactured components, where the thermal bonding of the extruded tracks to each other is typically considerably weaker than that in the direction of the raster orientation. Furthermore the thermal bonding, or fusing between individual layers can also lead to failure of components through the delamination of the individual layers themselves and the influence of toolpathing and raster directions on the strength of FFF parts has been the subject of in depth investigations previously [9]. Consequently the reinforcement provided by the inclusion of short fibre fillers does not provide significant inter layer reinforcement of the part but rather provides intra layer reinforcement in the individually extruded composite tracks, as with other composite manufacturing techniques

Curved Layer Fused Filament Fabrication describes a toolpathing technique for FFF that incorporates extruded tracks that contain dynamic z values as opposed to traditional methods that use static z values [10]. The use of this process allows individual extruded tracks to extend dynamically in all three dimensions and thus can be used to tailor the locations of individual track boundaries. The process is typically limited to smooth sloping surfaces owing to geometrical constraints discussed in the literature [11], but can be applied to a variety of useful geometries such as curved panels providing an improved finish to the surface quality of such components by removing step like characteristics that are typically present in the surfaces of FFF components. This study demonstrates manufacturing and preliminary mechanical testing of short fibre reinforced samples produced using CLFFF toolpathing methods that demonstrate reinforcement of samples in a dynamic plane.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Parallel FFF system

A key improvement in CLFFF manufacturing has been the incorporation of parallel, or delta, robots to FFF. These robot designs, first envisaged by Clavel [12], have been adapted from industrial pick and place robots to provide low cost FFF systems that can offer significant advantages over more traditional Cartesian style machines. In particular parallel robots offer true 3D movement of the tool head in all directions whereas many Cartesian systems can only provide significantly slower speeds in the build direction, typically as a result of most designs requiring the movement of the full print bed structure. Consequently using CLFFF on Cartesian systems has only seen limited application thus far, as the resulting increase in manufacturing speeds has hindered progress [11]. In this study we utilise an open source desktop parallel FFF system, a Rostock MAX V2 [2], to conduct CLFFF manufacturing. The system is detailed in **Figure 1A** with key components labelled. The static build plate and large build volume of this system make it an ideal choice for demonstrating CLFFF. A commercially available all-metal extruder [13] has also been installed on the system in order to allow thermal extrusion at the higher temperatures required for the feed stocks in use in this work. The extruder is mounted below the effector plate in order to allow additional clearance for CLFFF and is also detailed in **Figure 1B**.

Figure 1: (A) Overview of the Rostock MAX V2 parallel FFF system with key features labelled, (B) All-metal thermal extruder and deposition nozzle used throughout this study.

2.2 CLFFF Toolpathing

Although a number of studies have demonstrated various methods for the calculation of CLFFF toolpaths [10,11], using similar methods to those that are seen in advanced CNC machining techniques, no suitable software was available to generate toolpaths for the desired samples at the time of this study. Consequently a custom program was designed in MATLAB to allow the generation of simple CLFFF toolpaths and is currently undergoing continued development and testing at Bristol. This software was used to generate both conventional and CLFFF tensile test specimens. The process in use in this study relies on the use of a support structure and buffer release layer that support the CLFFF structure during manufacture. The use of support materials in FFF is common to increase the flexibility of the manufacturing process by enabling the fabrication of complex overhanging regions of printed components. In advanced FFF techniques a soluble support is often deposited from a second nozzle attached to the tool head. When using CLFFF it is critical that the tool head is kept to a minimum size in order to avoid collisions with the component during manufacturing. As a result the use of conventional dual extruders is not feasible however CLFFF lends itself to constructing its own support materials through using a single extruder. This process is conducted by the manufacturing of a part specific raft structure and buffer layer in order to support the final part during manufacturing. In this study the aim is to provide in-plane reinforcement to CLFFF samples manufactured at 30° to the plane of the build platform so only simple banked support structures are required although far more complex structures can be created as required. An angle of 30° is chosen as this represents a large but viable angle for conducting CLFFF. Support structures and buffer layers are also used in the manufacture of conventionally toolpathed samples in order to account for any effects the inclusion of raft and buffer structures may have. For simplicity in this scenario support rafts are manufacturing from Polylactide (PLA) feedstock as it represents a low cost readily available feedstock material for FFF. The buffer layer is manufactured using a proprietary Thermoplastic Elastomer (TPE) [14], which only bonds weakly to the other feed stocks in use in this work when undergoing thermal fusion through extrusion. Consequently parts can be mechanically released from the buffer layer and raft structure post manufacturing. **Figure 2** provides combined visualisations of the two toolpaths in use in this work as well as an example of more complex structures that have been fabricated using virgin feed stocks and CLFFF previously. In each case the samples sizing is designed in accordance with ASTM D638 [15] and details of the coupons precise size are also demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: (A) Conventional Toolpath including raft and buffer structures visualised in Repetier-Host software [16], with magnified detail of individual layer structures, (B) Equivalent toolpath visualisation for CLFFF component, (C) Specifications of ASTM D638 test specimens used in this study, (D) Example of a more complex CLFFF surface manufactured using virgin PLA showing the potential and limitations of this technique.

2.3 Short Fibre Composite Feedstock

Earlier studies have investigated the use of short fibres for reinforcement of FFF feed stocks previously, often observing successful reinforcement of manufactured components in the form of increased modulus and ultimate strength. Recent examples of short fibre feed stocks include the reinforcement of epoxy inks with Short Carbon Fibres [4] as discussed previously, but also the reinforcement of thermoplastic feed stocks such as ABS with short glass fibres amongst other modifying fillers has been demonstrated to be effective [7] Although some fibre reinforced filaments are becoming available commercially little is currently known about the quality control of the manufacture of such filaments or their precise composition. Consequently this study uses a filament produced in house from a commercially available glass fibre reinforced Nylon PA6 resin [17]. The thermoplastic resin contains 30 wt% of short glass fibres that are chosen as the reinforcing fibres in this work. Short glass fibres are preferred to carbon in order to allow non-destructive analysis of the orientations of the short fibres within FFF structures through the use of x-ray micro tomography (μ -CT) as the use of μ -CT to identify carbon fibre in a thermoplastic matrix is challenging. Feedstock material is produced in the form of a 2.75 mm diameter filament using a low cost desktop extruder

system [18]. Although this system is not ideal for the manufacturing of large scale quantities of FFF feed stocks it is capable of manufacturing small batches of filament that are suitable for initial preliminary testing of feedstock materials. Typically this process can produce tolerances better than ± 0.05 mm in virgin feedstock thermoplastic resins. In this case the inclusion of the fibrous filler appears to have affected the consistency of the extrusion and consequently larger variations were observed. As a result it was necessary to select suitable lengths of extruded feedstock for use in sample production by careful monitoring of the filament diameter. **Figure 3** details μ -CT scan data of as received reinforced Nylon pellets used in the manufacture of feedstock short fibre composite filaments revealing the presence of the glass fibre reinforcements.

Figure 3: Example μ -CT scan data of an as received glass fibre reinforced Nylon pellet, the fibres can be easily identified within the thermoplastic matrix.

2.4 Tensile Testing

As stated samples are manufactured following sizing specifications defined in Figure 2 and following ASTM D638. In each case three samples were manufactured and tested in order to identify if in plane reinforcement observed in conventional samples in the literature could be translated into CLFFF specimens, thus providing tailored reinforcement to a dynamic plane of the sample. Tensile testing is conducted at a low strain rate of 2 mm/min and data is sampled at a rate of 10 ms^{-1} using a Shimadzu AGS-X Universal testing machine. As only preliminary testing is conducted in order to assess the feasibility of marrying CLFFF and short fibre composite FFF feed stocks detailed strain analysis through the use of a video gauge system is not conducted in this study, although the gauge length and other variables were kept constant throughout testing.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Manufacturing of Test Specimens

Each specimen was manufactured individually using the Rostock MAX V2 printer described previously. The PLA raft structure is constructed using typical low quality PLA manufacturing in order to produce the raft structure as quickly as possible to reduce manufacturing time. As the raft does not form part of the final structure its mechanical performance and aesthetic quality need only be sufficient for the purpose of supporting the buffer layer. Consequently it can be manufactured using conventional toolpathing, and in this case toolpaths are generated using the open source software Cura [19]. To improve the lower surface of the final part buffer layers are manufactured using CLFFF

toolpaths in the precise plane of the lower surface of the final part geometry. This provides an ideal surface for depositing the first layer of the CLFFF component and has been demonstrated effectively using virgin polymers such as in Figure 2D. As each part of the structure is manufactured it is necessary to perform manual changes of the feedstock material in the Rostock's thermoplastic extruder, and to purge any remaining feedstock from the extrusion nozzle. Final test coupons are manufactured using a layer thickness of 0.2 mm and a 0.5 mm diameter extrusion nozzle thus resulting in coupons that consist of sixteen individually deposited layers. Composite feedstock material is deposited at a rate of 30 mm s^{-1} and a nozzle temperature of $280 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, following the appropriate toolpaths as shown in Figure 2A & 2B. Once manufacturing of a coupon is completed it can be removed from the build plate and then mechanically removed from the raft structure using simple hand tools. **Figure 4** details various manufacturing stages used for both conventional and CLFFF samples.

Figure 4: (A) Conventional specimen during the final stages of manufacturing, (B) Deposition of the CLFFF buffer layer using dynamic z toolpath vectors, (C) CLFFF specimen during the final stages of manufacturing, (D) Mechanical removal of the raft and buffer structure of a conventional sample using long nosed pliers.

The authors note that manufactured samples appear to be of a lower aesthetic quality than typically expected of FFF specimens. This is largely attributed to the simplicity of the toolpath generator employed in this work. The generator has been specifically modified to remove typically FFF toolpath features such as perimeters in order to avoid stress concentrations in components as have been

observed in other works previously [20], consequently resulting in a reduction in the aesthetic appearance of test coupons.

3.2 Tensile Testing Results

Preliminary tensile test results are plotted in **Figure 5** and are used to calculate the ultimate strength of each specimen. These values are listed for each specimen in **Table 1**. The results indicate that the samples manufactured using CLFFF only demonstrate an ultimate tensile strength of 70 % of samples manufactured using conventional toolpathing methods.

Figure 5: Tensile Stress-Extension plots used to calculate ultimate strength for reinforced Nylon specimens manufactured using conventional and CLFFF toolpathing techniques.

Specimen	Ultimate Strength/MPa	Group Average/MPa
Conventional 1	97.5	97.9
Conventional 2	94.8	
Conventional 3	101.3	
CLFFF 1	71.0	68.3
CLFFF 2	72.3	
CLFFF 3	61.6	

Table 1: Ultimate tensile strength results for tested specimens.

3.3 SEM Analysis of Specimen Fracture Surfaces

Scanning electron microscopy was conducted on the fracture surfaces of tested samples in order to investigate if localised alignment of the fibres within the planes of the layers and indeed individual

tracks of extruded composite feedstock had been achieved. **Figure 6** pictures typical electron micrographs of samples fracture surfaces that were observed using a Hitachi TM3030 Plus desktop SEM.

Figure 6: Electron Micrographs of composite specimen tensile fracture surfaces. (A) View perpendicular to fracture cross section revealing voids from fibre pull out (black arrows), and protruding glass fibres (white arrows) within the extrusion track vector orientation. (B) View parallel to the fracture cross section revealing fibres of greater than 100 μm in length protruding from the surface.

4 DISCUSSIONS

Tensile test specimens have been successfully fabricated using a tailored algorithm for generation of conventional and CLFFF toolpaths that lie parallel and at 30° to the build surface in FFF. Fabricated specimens demonstrate the feasibility of confining short fibres within dynamic layers of additive manufactured components by combining composite feedstock materials and CLFFF toolpathing techniques. Although some difficulties were observed during manufacture, likely owing to the quality of feedstock filament in use at this stage, the FFF was conducted in an identical fashion to virgin

polymer manufacture and overall aesthetic results are similar when considering the simplified toolpath generation software in use. Quality of manufacture can be assessed by comparing the results of the manufacturing process in Figure 4, with Repetier-Host gcode visualisations in Figure 2 which detail the precise toolpaths used during the manufacturing process.

Mechanical testing of tensile specimens demonstrated that the short fibre composite feedstock has been successfully used in FFF with conventional samples demonstrating average ultimate strengths of 97.9 MPa. For comparison the manufacturer's data sheet for moulded parts suggests tensile yield strengths of 110-175 MPa depending on part conditioning [17]. It should be noted however that injection moulded parts are expected to consist of uniform random fibre orientation due to thorough mixing of the composite during processing, unlike FFF components where anisotropic properties are expected. In comparison the CLFFF parts only achieved an average ultimate strength of 68.3 MPa, only 69.8 % of that achieved with conventional toolpathing. A number of causes are proposed as to the reason for this reduction in mechanical performance and are the subject of ongoing investigations currently. Firstly, in conventional toolpaths the extruder nozzle remains perpendicular to the vector of the deposited track, however as dynamic z components are introduced there is potential for the nozzle to effect the extruded material bead, particularly on steeper surfaces. Furthermore CLFFF manufacturing in this study includes a much larger raft structure than the conventional toolpath FFF process. As a consequence mechanical removal of the raft structure without damaging the specimen is challenging as the raft strength is similar to that of the specimen owing to the small cross section of the tensile specimens. Finally, CLFFF specimens may be effected by a greater thermal gradient than conventional samples, as a consequence of the overall height of the raft structure exceeding 60 mm. As the print bed is heated on the Rostock system, uneven cooling of the extruded tracks may occur in individual layers that is not seen in conventional FFF parts. It is proposed that these problems can be minimised by minor modifications to the manufacturing process, for example through refined deposition nozzle design and the use of a heated build chamber to reduce thermal gradients in the dynamic build volume.

Electron micrographs of fracture surfaces reveal general alignment of short glass fibres within the vector orientation of the extruded tracks inside individual manufactured layers. The micrographs also demonstrate regions of fibre pull out during specimen failure that is common in short fibre composite fracture surfaces. This result demonstrates that there is potential for providing tailored reinforcement to CLFFF structures through the use of the nylon/glass fibre composite feedstock material in use. The fracture surfaces do appear to reveal some porosity in the microstructure of the printed specimens although precise characterisation of the as manufactured microstructures is challenging from SEM images. It is thought that such porosity could occur as a result of insufficient extrusion of the feedstock which could be caused as a result of inconsistencies in feedstock filament diameter although further investigation into porosity of composite specimens and suitability of the feedstock in use is ongoing.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the manufacture of short fibre composite specimens from a glass fibre reinforced nylon feedstock material. Preliminary testing and observations have revealed confinement of short fibres within static and dynamic planes. Electron micrographs have revealed fully wetted short fibres within specimens with lengths that exceed the individual layer thickness of 200 μm thus adding a degree of alignment through the thermal extrusion of the feedstock through the deposition nozzle. Mechanical testing of components demonstrated a reduction in the ultimate strength of CLFFF coupons when compared with conventional counterparts. The mechanical performance of the conventional samples achieved an average of 89 % of the lower end of the manufacturer's range for ultimate strength indicating a similar build quality as observed in other works [20]. Even so the current manufacturing process will require refinement before a firm conclusion relating to the mechanical performance of CLFFF and conventional parts can be drawn. It is hoped that future studies will investigate the microstructure of manufactured specimens in depth through the use of $\mu\text{-CT}$ analysis in order to assess the global alignment of the short fibre reinforcements and also to identify any porosity in the samples. Furthermore it will be desirable to investigate if precise tailoring of toolpath vector

directions can tailor reinforcement in additive manufactured components in a similar method to traditional composite ply angles.

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